

A Conceptual Framework for an Inclusive Support System: The Underrepresentation of Women in ICT

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Abstract. The ICT sector is growing rapidly, leading to high job demands in the market. However, despite this growth, there is a concerning decline in the representation of women in the field. This issue has become a global crisis, especially in the context of achieving a Society 5.0 community. The underrepresentation of women in ICT is driven by various factors that women face both in educational settings; the society and at the workplace.

By applying the “Individual Differences Theory of Gender and Information Technology” framework, this paper presents a systematic literature review (SLR) of 29 studies, aimed at identifying and discussing the barriers contributing to the underrepresentation of women in ICT. Additionally, it explores ways in which women can take responsibility for reshaping the field to foster greater gender inclusion.

The findings highlight the key barriers identified in the literature that contribute to this underrepresentation, and propose strategic measures that women can adopt to transform the ICT field for greater gender inclusivity. In conclusion, a conceptual framework is developed, which outlines strategic actions and provides a toolkit to address the challenges women face in both educational and workplace environments, ultimately reshaping the ICT field for enhanced gender inclusivity.

Keywords: Information Communication and Technology, Gender; Inclusivity; Underrepresentation, Women, Society 5.0

1 Introduction

The gender imbalance in the ICT field represents a significant diversity deficit. Despite the growing demand for skills within the sector [2], the representation of women remains disproportionately low. This is particularly evident in artificial intelligence (AI), one of the fastest-growing subfields in ICT. AI is driving the world toward a digital economy, underscoring the rapid expansion of the ICT industry [1]. However, as the field grows, the participation of women remains stagnant.

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Studies across various countries reveal a consistent gender imbalance in the ICT industry [3], [4], [5], [35], [37]. For example, research from Bangladesh's Open-Source Network shows that only 25% of women in Bangladesh are pursuing ICT degrees [4]. This underrepresentation is not a new issue; it was first identified in the late 20th century [5]. Societal gender norms often lead girls to believe ICT degrees are primarily for men, steering them toward fields like health and social sciences [6]. As a result, fewer women pursue ICT careers, and even fewer continue in the industry long-term [4]. Research by Tahsin et al. indicates that only 13% of female ICT graduates enter the workforce, with that figure dropping to 10% as women often leave the industry due to various challenges, including gender discrimination [4].

Gender discrimination is a major barrier to diversity in the ICT field [7]. Women who remain in the industry often have to empower themselves through initiatives like coding boot camps, where they can find support and encouragement from other women [7]. These efforts are crucial for breaking down barriers and improving gender inclusion within the ICT sector.

The relationship between women's representation and the growth of the ICT field is inversely proportional [8]. While there is a high demand for ICT skills, the industry continues to be male-dominated [1], and this gender gap poses risks. For example, many tech products are developed from a male perspective, which can result in both deliberate and inadvertent biases [1]. This lack of diversity in development teams contributes to stereotypical technology solutions, limiting the potential of future innovations [9].

Addressing the gender gap in ICT is critical for fostering a more inclusive environment that drives diverse technological solutions [1]. To attract more women into the field, it's vital to emphasize the role that women in ICT play in reshaping the industry. Their presence in communities such as Society 5.0 and events can inspire future generations of women to pursue ICT careers. Society 5.0 refers to a concept of a society driven by technological advancements that envisions the integration of the physical and digital worlds through the use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) to create a "super-smart society" [34]. This vision includes a sustainable and inclusive socio-economic system, powered by digital technologies such as big data analytics, artificial intelligence (AI), the Internet of Things (IoT), and robotics [34].

The "Individual Differences Theory of Gender and Information Technology" [10] is a theoretical framework used to identify the various factors, classified as environmental, identity, and individual influences, that contribute to the underrepresentation of women in ICT. Based on this framework, the following research questions guide this systematic literature review:

1. What factors (environmental, identity and individual) contribute to the underrepresentation of women in the ICT field?
2. What measures (in the form of a strategic framework) can women take to achieve equal representation in the ICT field, considering the future development of a community driven by Society 5.0

The strategic framework developed as a result of this research may support various stakeholders, including women in the ICT sector, in addressing the factors—classified according to the Individual Differences Theory of Gender and Information Technology—that contribute to the underrepresentation of women in the field.

2 Literature Background

The integration of science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) is currently marked by the lowest level of female representation [11]. For instance, a study by Adams and Morgan [2] in Australia, which examined female representation in STEM faculties, found that women make up only 13% of technological departments, compared to 23% in science and 35% in mathematics [2]. This gap is primarily due to the limited number of women pursuing ICT careers after high school, which negatively affects the ICT industry. Jurado, Tretiakov, and Bensemann [8] emphasize the widespread underrepresentation of women in the ICT sector across various countries. Their figures, recorded in 2018, show the proportion of women in the ICT industry by country. The countries listed are as follows: India ranks first with 34%, Australia

follows in second place with 30%, Turkey ranks third at 28%, and the United Kingdom ranks last at 16% [8]. Additionally, Hyrynsalmi [12] highlights that women in the U.S. hold only 11% of managerial positions in the ICT sector.

The difficulty of balancing work and family responsibilities often prevents women from seeking managerial roles, and the industry's pressures contribute to many women leaving the field, further reducing female representation in leadership positions [5]. This phenomenon is a global trend.

In the past, the ICT industry was predominantly female, but this rapidly changed over time. In 1984, 37% of computer science majors were women, but by 2020, this figure had dropped to 18% [1]. Socio-cultural expectations and traditional gender biases, along with stereotyping, have contributed to this decline. These factors have created barriers for women pursuing ICT degrees and careers.

Socio-cultural expectations and gender narratives affect various stages of a woman's life [9]. First, girls often encounter educational barriers that limit their exposure to ICT. A study [12] found that while girls outperform boys in STEM subjects in high school, few women pursue ICT degrees, suggesting a lack of awareness or guidance about ICT career paths. Adams and Morgan [2] found that many students were unfamiliar with the specifics of a Computer Science degree, highlighting a gap in exposure to computing and ICT fields.

Second, male dominance remains prevalent in the ICT industry. For example, a study at Universidad de la República in Uruguay showed that only 15% of female students were pursuing ICT degrees, compared to 20% of male students [6]. Women also represent only 18% of leadership roles in artificial intelligence research, while men make up 80% [1], underscoring the gender imbalance in the field.

Finally, women in ICT face challenges that often drive them to leave the industry. The lack of female representation in leadership roles contributes to mistreatment and marginalization [13]. Friedmann and Efrat-Treister [14] note that gender bias in hiring practices often leads to male candidates being preferred over female candidates. Additionally, many women leave the sector after maternity leave due to the difficulty of balancing new parental responsibilities with the demands of high-performance work in ICT [5]. Socialized gender norms about domestic duties and the pressure to meet work expectations frequently prevent women from returning to ICT roles after maternity leave.

Despite these challenges, women have taken steps to drive diversity and inclusion in the ICT industry. For example, Fonseca et al. [35] indicate how policies evolved through COVID and what progress was made to address digital equality. Efforts such as workshops, policies, institutional reforms, mentorship programs, and the creation of software community groups are slowly leading to more gender diversification within the sector [35], [36]. Genut and Kolikant [16] highlight an increase in women studying bioinformatics, reflecting a shift toward greater gender inclusion in ICT fields such as biology and information systems.

3 Research Method

The research conducted is a systematic literature review. According to Lame [17], a systematic literature review is a method of using multiple published sources to answer a research question. This process involves analysing and evaluating these sources to build an understanding of the findings and address the research question.

The data sources included: Scopus, ScienceDirect, IEEE Xplore Digital Library and Web of Science Core Collection.

The following search string was used: (“Underrepresentation”) AND (“Girls” OR “Women” OR “Females”) AND (“Information Communication Technology” OR “Information Technology” OR “Technology” OR “ICT” OR “IT” OR “Tech”).

The papers selected in this research study complied with the inclusion criteria as presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Selection criteria

Inclusion criteria
1. Papers published between 2018 and 2024, as the field of ICT is rapidly evolving, necessitating recent studies for a comprehensive evaluation.
2. Papers written exclusively in English.
3. Papers with full access to the complete text, including the abstract, introduction, discussion, methods, conclusion, and references.
4. Peer-reviewed papers from published literature, including peer-reviewed journals and articles.
5. Papers directly related to the topic of study

3.1 Prisma Flowchart

A Prisma flowchart is a diagram that outlines the breakdown of papers identified for analysis. Using the search string, a total of 736 papers were found across all the specified databases. The use of multiple databases resulted in 45 duplicate papers, leaving a final set of 691 papers. These were then screened by reviewing the abstracts and keywords. Following the screening protocol, 613 papers were excluded, leaving 78. After a full evaluation of the remaining papers, 49 were excluded, resulting in a total of 29 papers selected for this systematic literature review as indicated in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: Prisma flowchart

4 Findings and Discussion

4.1 Findings

This section presents the general findings from the 29 papers identified using the process described in the Prisma Flowchart in Section 3.

4.1.1 Descriptive Analysis of Literature Sources

Table 2 shows the distribution of selected papers across the databases used for this literature review from 2018 to 2024. Scopus has the highest number of selected papers, with 15, while ScienceDirect has the lowest, with only 1.

Table 2: Papers by database source

Source	Count	%
ScienceDirect	1	3.4
Scopus	15	51.7
IEEE Xplore	8	27.6
Web of Science Core Collection	5	17.3

4.1.2 Thematic Analysis

In this section, thematic analysis, as defined by Naeem, Ozuem, Howell and Ranfagni [18] is performed using VOSviewer, a tool for visualizing data networks. A network map, shown in Figure 3, was created through a keyword/code co-occurrence analysis

[19].

The lines in the map represent the relationships between keywords, while the circles indicate the number of research papers featuring each keyword. Larger circles signify keywords that appear in more papers, as detailed in Section 4.3 [19]. The map also features color-coded clusters, which are further interpreted in Table 3, based on the data network map in Figure 2.

Fig. 2: Data network map based on authors keywords

Table 3: Interpretation of relevant identified clusters

Cluster	Colour	Keywords/Codes	Thematic analysis
Cluster 1	Blue	Gender difference in STEM Career Choice Computer science education	The themes focus on the gender differences encountered by women in STEM and the implications of their career choices in computer science education
Cluster 2	Green	IT exclusion dynamics	The themes focus on the exclusion dynamics faced by girls in ICT and how these dynamics influence their career choices
Cluster 3	Yellow	Ability to work long hours Gender bias	The themes address the expectation that women must work long hours to be perceived as competent.
Cluster 4	Red	Gender stereotypes, bias and awareness	The themes focus on gender stereotypes, biases, and awareness

4.2 Discussion of Findings

The aim of this paper is to examine the challenges contributing to the underrepresentation of women in the ICT field and explore how women are taking control of their futures within it. Historical events have shaped the relationship between women and technology, contributing to the low representation of women in ICT. This underrepresentation is recognized as a global crisis, as current software and technological solutions are predominantly developed from a male perspective. This results in the exclusion of women from society, as future ICT products may be designed to cater primarily to men.

The findings in this paper also highlight the barriers leading to the underrepresentation of women in ICT. The "Individual Differences Theory of Gender and Information Technology (IT)" framework [10] is applied to identify three key categories: Environmental Factors, Influential Individuality Factors, and Identity Factors. The clusters identified in the thematic analysis (Table 3) are organized according to the three key categories of the Individual Differences Theory of Gender and Information Technology.

Serenko and Turel [10] define *environmental factors* as the impact of society's behavior, culture, and economic state on an individual. This systematic literature review explores how environmental factors create barriers to women entering the ICT field. The following environmental factors are identified in the findings:

1. **Workplace Environment (Cluster 2, 3, 4: Table 3):** A culture rooted in hypermasculinity, competitiveness, and gendered expectations is often unwelcoming to women [5]. As a result, many women leave the ICT field due to performance anxiety, unhealthy working conditions and exclusion from the work environment [4].
2. **Work-Life Balance (Cluster 3: Table 3):** The ICT field is constantly evolving, with new skills required to keep up with its rapid changes. As a result, professionals in this field must continuously upskill to stay current [5]. Additionally, Tretiakov, Bensemann, and Jurado [5] note that the ICT field is high-pressure, characterized by demanding workloads, strict deadlines, and projects that require 24/7 attention. This often leads to the need for overtime work. However, for women in the ICT field, balancing upskilling and overtime can be challenging. Societal expectations often place women in traditional family roles [11], where they are expected to prioritize family and household responsibilities over career ambitions. Guo, Eccles, Sortheix, and Salmela-Aro [11] highlight that women in traditional households are expected to focus on caregiving, while men are often viewed as the breadwinners, expected to prioritize work over family duties. This reinforces the stereotype that women cannot work overtime due to societal expectations of managing household responsibilities [14]. It's important to note that the assumption that all women struggle with work-life balance is a generalized stereotype.
3. **Gender Biases in Hiring (Cluster 2: Table 3):** In the ICT field, men are hired more frequently than women, largely due to discrimination during the interview process [14]. Women face both conscious and unconscious biases, including the expectation to work overtime due to household responsibilities, which hinders their entry into the workforce [14]. Furthermore, male managers tend to exhibit gender favouritism, favouring male candidates over female ones during the hiring process [14].
4. **Societal Expectations (Cluster 4: Table 3):** Society often defines how women should behave, reinforcing gender divisions in the ICT field. The theory of social constructionism shapes how women and men are treated in society by establishing predefined gender expectations and identity attributes for each gender [8]. This theory contributes to the creation of gender differences, which influence how both genders are perceived within society [8]. Social constructionism manifests through several key ideas: First, it perpetuates the perception that women are less competent than their male counterparts. Second, it promotes the idea that the ICT field is more suitable for men. Third, it fosters the belief that men are inherently smarter than women [20]. Moreover, social constructionism impacts career decisions for girls and women, as noted by Tanwir and Khemka [20]. Their survey in Pakistan revealed that societal gender norms are a primary reason for the low representation of women in the IT sector. These norms prevent women and girls from pursuing education and careers in demanding fields like ICT. As a result, women in the ICT workforce are subjected to discrimination, rooted in societal norms and stereotypes.

Serenko and Turel [10] define *identity factors* as the mindset and behaviors of an individual. The following identity factors were identified:

1. **Lack of Career Guidance (Cluster 1: Table 3):** Career guidance plays a critical role during adolescence, as individuals are highly influenced by external factors when choosing their career paths [9]. In this regard, females are often discouraged from pursuing careers in ICT [9]. Family members, teachers, and friends play a key role in shaping the career decisions of females [9]. The tendency for females to choose non-technical degrees is frequently influenced by observing their mothers working in non-technical professions [9]. Moreover, educators have the most significant impact on females' career choices, as they guide students throughout their educational journey [9]. Consequently, the low representation of women in the ICT field can be attributed to the lack of encouragement from educators to consider careers in technology [8]. With limited awareness of technical STEM degrees, many women are drawn to fields like health or social sciences, where there is already a larger female presence.
2. **Imposter Syndrome and Computer Anxiety (Cluster 4: Table 3):** Computer anxiety arises from a lack of exposure to technology [21]. It often manifests as impostor syndrome and low self-esteem, both of which are common among women in the ICT field [21]. According to Tahsin, Ahmed, Asad, and Sakib [4], males are typically exposed to computing devices at an earlier age than females, which means they are less likely to experience computer anxiety, having had more time to become familiar with technology [21].

Influential individuality factors represent a set of characteristics that define an individual, including experiences [10]. The following influential individuality factors were identified:

1. **Lack of Role Models (Cluster 1, 2, 4: Table 3):** Role models are crucial in any sector. Tahsin, Ahmed, Asad, and Sakib [4] highlight that female role models are particularly important as they inspire younger women and spark their interest in the ICT field. The visible leadership of women in ICT motivates the younger generation of females [1]. However, the lack of women in leadership positions can discourage those considering an ICT degree [4]. As a result, the current absence of female representation in the ICT field contributes to the lack of interest among younger women [21].

Despite these challenges, women are actively reshaping the ICT industry and driving inclusion through various initiatives. These measures contribute to promoting gender equality:

1. **Mentorship Programs:** Female mentorship plays a pivotal role in increasing the representation of women in the ICT field [20]. Mentorship programs create opportunities for girls to interact with female role models in the industry, which fosters greater interest in ICT careers. These programs offer career guidance, educational opportunities, and peer support to participants [21]. Over the years, the ICT sector has seen a rise in female mentorship initiatives aimed at inspiring and empowering women and girls [3]. For example, the Million Women Mentors program focuses on educating girls and women about STEM careers while providing individualized support [3]. Other notable mentorship organizations include the IEEE Women in Computing Society, Girls Can Code, and Women in Technology [3], [21].
2. **Coding Boot Camps:** Coding boot camps are intensive programs designed to teach fundamental concepts in software development, data science, artificial intelligence, and cybersecurity, typically over a period of three months [7]. These boot camps provide girls and women with valuable coding skills, encouraging them to explore and pursue careers in the technology industry.

The rise of mentorship programs and coding boot camps is helping to attract girls in high school and women seeking to transition into ICT careers. These programs are providing women with the resources and support to overcome barriers and contribute to a more inclusive and diverse ICT field. Through these efforts, women are creating a visible path for change in the industry.

5 Towards a Conceptual Framework for Women to Reshape the ICT Field

The conceptual framework in Figure 3 outlines strategic measures women can take to reshape the ICT field for equal representation and opportunities. The findings of this paper reveal that women face challenges in entering the ICT field, influenced by their environment, which is divided into two key areas: the workplace and the educational environment. This division, illustrated in the framework, aims to provide targeted solutions for the unique challenges in each area. The framework identifies the root causes of these issues and organizes them into construct categories. Figure 3 visually represents the framework, emphasizing the strategic measures women can use as a toolkit to transform the ICT field and promote equal representation for an inclusive community such as Society 5.0.

Fig. 3: Conceptual Framework - strategic measures taken by women in reshaping the ICT field

Table 4 presents a breakdown of strategic measures that women can take to reshape the ICT field. It outlines various actions grouped into specific construct categories. The construct categories applicable to the workplace include inclusive hiring, supportive work environments, and flexible work policies. Additionally, the construct categories relevant to the educational environment are career guidance and technical upskilling.

Table 4: Strategic Measures for Women to Reshape the ICT Field.

Environment	Construct Category	Example
Measures for the workplace	Inclusive hiring practices	Diverse hiring panel Use non-bias recruitment technology
	Supportive working environment	Provide a day care centre at work Ensure job security Offer support after maternity leave
	Flexible Work Policies	Remote work Flexible schedule No overtime
Measures for the education environment	Career guidance	Mentorship programs Networking events Career expo
	Technical upskilling	Coding bootcamps Funding for ICT degrees

These construct categories are explained in more detail:

Measures to be Taken in the Workplace Environment

1. **Inclusive Hiring Practices:** Women are often subjected to gender bias during job interviews, largely due to the male-dominated hiring panels and the use of biased recruitment technologies. To address this, strategic measures should include forming diverse hiring panels and implementing unbiased recruitment technologies to eliminate gender biases in the hiring process.
2. **Supportive Working Environment:** The lack of support in the workplace manifests in several ways. For example, pregnant women in managerial positions are often treated differently from their male counterparts, with their work ethic harshly criticized, which can hinder their chances of receiving salary increases. Additionally, women often face challenges balancing overtime work with household responsibilities, which can lead to perceptions of incompetence and increase the risk of job loss. To address these issues, the following strategic measures can be implemented:
 - a. Companies can provide on-site childcare services for employees working overtime.
 - b. Employers can ensure job security for all employees, particularly those returning from maternity leave.
 - c. Companies should offer additional support for women after maternity leave to help them reintegrate into the workplace.
3. **Flexible Work Policies:** Women often face challenges in achieving work-life balance. To address this, the following strategic measures can be implemented:
 - a. Companies should offer remote work options.
 - b. Flexible working schedules should be provided to help accommodate household responsibilities.
 - c. Overtime work should be voluntary, allowing employees to maintain a healthy work-life balance.

Measures to be Taken in the Education Environment

1. **Career Guidance:** Women and girls often choose to pursue degrees in health sciences and humanities due to limited career guidance and exposure to career opportunities. To increase the number of women and girls interested in studying ICT-related degrees, several strategic measures can be implemented. First, career expos and mentorship programs can provide platforms for exposure to the ICT industry and offer access to career mentors. Additionally, networking events can connect women with a community of other women

already working in the ICT field.

2. **Technical Upskilling:** Women often experience computer anxiety, and coding bootcamps can help bridge the technical gap they face.

6 Conclusion

This paper continues the discourse on the underrepresentation of women in the ICT field and industry. Using a systematic literature review (SLR) of 29 studies, the paper aims to identify and discuss the barriers contributing to this underrepresentation (research question 1). Additionally, it explores ways in which women can take an active role in reshaping the field to foster greater gender inclusion, especially in preparation for future societies such as Society 5.0 (research question 2).

By applying the "Individual Differences Theory of Gender and Information Technology" [10], the barriers to women's participation in the ICT field are categorized into three areas: environmental factors, influential individuality factors, and identity factors. Environmental factors focus on workplace culture, which is often shaped by misogyny and challenges related to work-life balance. Influential individuality factors highlight the lack of mentorship opportunities for women in ICT, while identity factors examine the lack of career guidance and the negative attitudes many women hold, often due to limited exposure to technology.

This paper proposes potential solutions to overcome these barriers, emphasizing the importance of mentorship programs and coding bootcamps as key strategies for increasing women's representation in the field. A conceptual framework is derived from the theoretical framework, focusing on strategic measures that women can take to reshape the ICT field and promote greater inclusion in future societies, where women can contribute equally alongside their male counterparts. The framework emphasizes two environmental dimensions: the workplace and educational settings, advocating for inclusive hiring, supportive work environments, flexible policies, career guidance, and technical upskilling.

In conclusion, addressing the gender representation crisis through awareness and targeted measures can help dismantle the barriers identified in this paper. The solutions proposed in the conceptual framework provide actionable steps to overcome these challenges.

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